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“CLASSROOM VOICES OF THE SELF”

As I first entered our classroom door,
the students seem unfamiliar, but some I had met before

They looked so innocent, and sweet
but with wondering faces of strangers, they meet.

That's why, I asked them honest yet true,
a simple question: who are you?

And silence began.

Preparing of sharing they could not outrun

One by one prepare to stand
and share in class as creatively they can.

Some proudly spoke who of they are
their hobbies, dreams and hope afar.

Some spoke in slow and soft voice.

Told us that being alone is their choice,
that their life is good,

In solitude quite mood.

They called themselves introvert

But deep inside unconsciously hurts.

Others describe themselves with a loud voice.

Told us about family, friends,
place and culture were their choice,

of better knowing themselves self,
they cherish and enjoy.

Hearing their answers,

reminds me that the self is understood in two ways,

One is individual and the other is communal.

In a quiet room, I told them that knowing the self

is not only by finding from within

but also, by shared experience and identity

where our lives grow and begin.

